

Impact of MGNREGP on Women Empowerment among Respondents of Tiruvannamalai District, Tamil Nadu, India

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Received: Sep 20, 2025

Accepted: Oct 16, 2025

Published: Dec 29, 2025

Abstract:

The empowerment of rural women is crucial for the development of Rural Bharat. Bringing women into the mainstream of development is a major concern for the Government of India, which is why 2001 was declared as the “Year of Women Empowerment”. The programme for poverty alleviation has a women’s component to ensure flow of adequate funds to this section. So, this study aims at understanding the impact of MGNREGP on the lives of women workers who have worked under this programme.

The study was undertaken in Tiruvannamalai District to study the role of MGNREGA scheme and its impact on the Upliftment of rural people. The study collected primary data through well-structured interview schedule from 540 respondents in the study area. The study used simple percentage analysis as statistical tool for analysis of data. The study analysed the income of the respondents before and after entering into the scheme in terms of adequacy of income to purchase sufficient food, dress, spend for their children’s education, for savings and to purchase of household assets. Tiruvannamalai district is one of the backward districts in Tamilnadu and 80 per cent of the people are living in rural areas. Unemployment is the major problem in India, especially the problem is more in rural areas among unskilled people and it leads to poverty in the country. In order to reduce poverty in rural area, the Government of India introduced Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. It was found that the scheme had given a considerable benefit to rural unemployed people in Thiruvannamalai district. The beneficiaries of the scheme got benefit in terms of adequacy of income to purchase sufficient food, dress, spend for children education, for savings and to purchase of household assets.

Keywords: *Empowerment, rural women, MGNREGP, purposive sampling, primary data, Unemployment and Income*

Introduction

Poverty eradication and women empowerment are essential for overall growth of a country. This will take the country to a developing path. So women empowerment is essential for rural women. The classical women's movement of the 19th and early 20th century was a movement by women for women. They sought fundamental change in gender relations by improving women's conditions from economic, social, political and cultural perspectives in comparison with their traditional situation and in comparison with men. Bagchi (2007) has pointed out women primarily dominated the home front. They did cooking for the family and often helped their husbands in other activities e.g. in agricultural operations (winnowing and husking) etc., Their importance in other spheres however, was not ephemeral women in ancient India being employed in industries as well as in the households. A perusal of the smritis and other ancient Indian scriptures reveals that women were employed either as Dasi (slaves or maid servants); or Ganika or as Karmakar (hired workers in agriculture and industry). According to Jain (2007), the United Nations world conference adopted the forward looking strategies for the advancement of women from 1986 to 2000 A.D. Empowerment is the most recent approach articulated by the 'Third World' women. It seeks to meet women's strategic gender needs, due to their subordinate position to men, through bottom up mobilization around practical gender needs according to their accepted role in society. It aims at increasing women's power in terms of their self-reliance and internal strength to determine choices in life and to influence the direction of change. Lalneihzovi (2007) has explained that women of Aryan and Dravidian societies suffer due to the burden of women's share (what the dowry used to mean in the past) and many women died for the same. Raju (2007) has emphasized the term empowerment of women as an important popular concept among political spectrum. Empowerment through the expansion of civil, political and social rights of citizenship is a laborious and unexciting process. Empowerment is only effective answer to oppression, exploitation, injustice, and other maladies of society. Empowerment is both a means to an end and an end in itself. The focus on empowerment has given a new emphasis to the building of economic and social capabilities among individuals, classes and communities. Mukherjee (2008) has explained that the principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its preamble, fundamental rights, fundamental duties and directive principle. The constitution not only grants equality to women but also empowers the state to adopt measures, a position, or indiscriminate in favour of women. Verma (2003) says that women play a crucial role in the empowerment of the family, group, society etc. Rural women usually get engaged in home and farm activities. Their contribution is invisible as they influence men, educate family and convince the people to accept change in development. This force is to be utilized in planning, execution, monitoring and assessment of poverty alleviation programmes for better results. Bhumali and Poddar (2005) have explained that the multiplicity of agencies has been carrying on the task of providing rural employment. They include Employment Guarantee Schemes, Food for Work Programme, Small Farmers Development Agency, Marginal Farmers and Agricultural labourers, Drought Prone Area Development etc., Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), National Rural Employment Programme (NREP) and Rural Landless Employment

Guarantee Programme (RLEGP). The Food for Work Programme was restricted and renamed as National Rural Employment programmes (NREP) since 1980. Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (TRYSEM) is centrally sponsored scheme. It started functioning since 15th August 1979. Banerjee (2005) says that poverty alleviation programmes would be formulated and implemented in a decentralized manner with the participation of people at the grass roots level. Banerjee and Saha (2010) observed that employment generation is necessary to raise the purchasing power, and thereby create demand in the economy. Maulick (2009) has explained that some of the positive features of NREGA are high share of female employment, benefits are reflected in greater economic security, higher farm wages, lower migration and building of infrastructure. The NREGA works are intended to create permanent assets in the rural areas for future needs. Sankari and Siva Murugan (2009) observed that the NREGP have a positive impact on the social and economic well-being of rural labourers and their families. In particular, it holds the powerful prospect of bringing major changes in the lives of women. This is especially true in a state like Tamil Nadu, where women constitute an overwhelming proportion (more than 80%) of NREGP workers. Pattanaik (2009) has explained that the women beneficiaries of MGNREGPs of Hoshiarpur district of Andhra Pradesh have opined that the income through this wage rate has helped the household to purchase low cost furniture, kitchen materials and even better cloths for their children and even spend on the education of the children purchase of books, copies and others need of their school going children. The income has enabled them to purchase additional amount of pulses, vegetables and other nutrition items for their households. Considering the above facts in view, this study analyzed the contribution made by women respondent's income to their family income, decision making status, savings and usefulness of MGNREGP

Objective

The study has been undertaken with the following objective.

To study role of MGNREGA scheme and its impact to uplift rural unemployed people in
Thiruvannamalai district

Methodology

The study was undertaken in Tiruvannamalai District to study the role of MGNREGA scheme and its impact to the upliftment of rural people. The study collected primary data through well-structured interview schedule from 540 respondents in the study area. The study used simple percentage analysis as statistical tool for analysis of data

Results and Interpretation

For the purpose of analyzing the role of MGNREGA scheme and its impact on the upliftment of rural people in Thiruvannamalai district, the study identified five major aspects namely Food, Dress and Education expenses of children are most important expenses to be spent

by the people after satisfied these expenditure they go for savings then they want to buy some assets such as house hold assets (television, refrigerator, mixer, grinder and so on). Hence the researcher analyzed position of the beneficiaries before and after entering into the scheme.

Adequacy of Income for Food

Food is the most important need of every human being. Poverty line in India was fixed on the basis of sufficiency of income to consume a minimum of 2400 calories per day for each member of a family. Table 1 presents results about adequacy of income for consuming food before and after enrolling into MGNREGA scheme.

Adequacy of Income for Food Table 1: Adequacy for Food Purchases

Adequacy for Food Purchase	Before Entering into MGNREGA		After Entering into MGNREGA	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	209	38.7	505	93.5
No	331	61.3	35	6.5
Total	540	100.0	540	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 report that 38.7 per cent of the respondents only told that they had an adequate income to buy sufficient food and 61.3 per cent of the respondents did not have adequate income to buy sufficient food before availing benefit under MGNREGA scheme. But after entering into the scheme, there was a drastic improvement in earnings of the respondents. The results showed that 93.5 per cent of the respondents had adequate income to buy sufficient food after entering into the scheme and 6.5 per cent of the respondents told that even after entering into the scheme they were not able to earn adequat income to buy sufficient food for their family, reason for this might be high number of family members or the beneficiary might engaged less number of days of work under MGNREGA scheme.

Table 2: Adequacy for Dress Purchases

Adequacy for Dress Purchase	Before Entering into MGNREGA		After Entering into MGNREGA	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	167	30.9	423	78.3
No	373	69.1	117	21.7
Total	540	100.0	540	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 reports that 69.1 per cent of the respondents did not earn adequate income to purchase dress for their family and 30.9 per cent of the respondents had adequate income to purchase dress before entering into the scheme. After entering into MGNREGA scheme 78.3 per cent of the respondents were able to earn adequate income to purchase dress for their family members and 21.7 per cent of the respondents did not have adequate income to purchase dress even after entering into MGNREGA scheme. It showed that there was considerable improvement in upliftment of rural poor in terms of adequacy of income to purchase dress.

Adequacy of Income to Spend for Children's Education

After fulfilling food and dress people would like to give good education for their children. In order to know benefit derived from MGNREGA scheme in terms of adequacy of income to spend for children education, adequacy of income before and after entering into the scheme were analysed and presented in table 3

Table 3: Adequacy of Income to Spend for Children's Education

Adequacy for Children Education	Before Entering into MGNREGA		After Entering into MGNREGA	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	156	28.9	452	83.7
No	384	71.1	88	16.3
Total	540	100.0	540	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 reports that 28.9 per cent of the respondents only were able to get adequate income to spend for their children education before entering into MGNREGA scheme, but 71.1 per cent of the respondents were not able to earn adequate income to spend for their children education. But after entering into the scheme 83.7 per cent of the respondents obtained adequate income to spend for their children education and 16.3 per cent of the respondents were not able to spend for their children education even after entering into MGNREGA scheme.

Adequacy of Income to Spend for Savings

Table 4 presents results about number of respondents and their respective percentage on total in terms of adequacy of income for savings before and after entering into MGNREGA scheme in the study area.

Adequacy for Savings	Before Entering into MGNREGA		After Entering into MGNREGA	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	106	19.6	377	69.8
No	434	80.4	163	30.2
Total	540	100.0	540	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 shows that 19.6 per cent of the respondents only had adequate income to make savings and 80.4 per cent of the respondents told that they did not have adequate income to make savings before availing benefit under MGNREGA scheme. But after entering into the scheme, there was a considerable improvement in earnings of the respondents and 69.8 per cent of the respondents had adequate income for

savings after entering into the scheme and 30.2 per cent of the respondents told that even after entering into the scheme they were not able to make savings.

Adequacy of Income for purchase of assets

After fulfilling necessary needs of people, they move for purchase of household assets such as furniture, television, mixer, grinder, refrigerator and so on. Table 5 presents results about number of respondents and their respective percentage who got adequate income for purchase of assets before and after entering into MGNREGA scheme

Table 5: Adequacy of Income for Purchase of Assets

Adequacy to buy Assets	Before Entering into MGNREGA		After Entering into MGNREGA	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	81	15.0	328	60.7
No	459	85.0	212	39.3
Total	540	100.0	540	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 reports that 15 per cent of the respondents only were able to get adequate income to purchase assets, but 85 per cent of the respondents were not able to earn adequate income for the purpose of purchase of assets before entering into the scheme. But after entering into the scheme 60.7 per cent of the respondents obtained adequate income to purchase household assets and 39.3 per cent of the respondents were not able to spend for purchase of assets even after entering into MGNREGA scheme

Conclusion

Thiruvannamalai district is one of the backward districts in Tamilnadu and 80 per cent of the people are living in rural areas. Unemployment is the major problem in India; especially the problem is more in rural areas among unskilled people and it leads for poverty in the country. In order to reduce poverty in rural area, the Government of India introduced Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. It was found that the scheme had given a considerable benefit to rural unemployed people in Thiruvannamalai district. The beneficiaries of the scheme got benefit in terms of adequacy of income to purchase sufficient food, dress, spend for children education, for savings and to purchase of household asset

There was an existence of unemployment in Tiruvannamalai district in agriculture during summer season. To avoid this seasonal employment, there was a necessity to work with MGNREGP. Even though they could not control the effects of poverty fully, there was a considerable improvement. Before the implementation of MGNREGP, more than half of the respondents from this area were below poverty line. But the situation was improved in terms of employment, increase in income, savings, willingness to buy essential goods and there was a considerable reduction in the level of poverty. Hence, we may conclude that MGNREGP have empowered the women respondents partially in the study area.

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